

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Nail Lacquer for Treatment of Onychomycosis

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 13 May 2025

Keywords:

Tea tree oil, castor oil, ethyl cellulose, nail lacquer, onychomycosis.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15398260

ABSTRACT

Nails are the hard and durable epidermal. The nail plate is responsible for the penetration of the drug across it. There is the number of formulations with antifungal agents viz. gels, creams, and oral antifungal for the treatment of transungual infections. Among these entire nail lacquers is a new concept in treating nail infections. These nail lacquers are effective as monotherapy in the treatment of superficial, distal, and subungual diseases. The medicated lacquer preparations are generally used in fungal diseases. Use of this system avoids oral toxicity of antifungal drugs. It is associated with the drug delivery through the hard keratinized nail plate to treat the diseases of the nail itself in conditions like onychomycosis and nail psoriasis. The goal of the current study was to create and formulate a therapeutic nail lacquer using the Neem oil to treat the condition of onychomycosis. Neem oil, an antifungal agent, was combined with castor oil, an established anti-inflammatory drug, in this study. Nail lacquer was made using a simple mixing process. Application frequency was decreased to twice a week by using polymers such ethyl cellulose to sustain medication release for up to 20 hours. In the present study, nail lacquer containing a permeation enhancer salicylic acid and release extender ethyl cellulose in different concentration is tried out and comparison of extend of drug permeation has been done among the same. Then, formulated nail lacquers were compared for physical appearance, drying time, non-volatile content, gloss, water resistance, drug content.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades the treatment of illness has been accomplished by Administrating drugs to human body via various routes namely oral,

parental, topical, Inhalation etc. Every medical condition demands an accurate and appropriate treatment. As a matter of fact, the thought of resolving the patient's disease with least harm done To the patient's health is said to be the basic

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

goal of any therapy. Moreover a good Treatment technique necessitates thorough knowledge of pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics of the intended drug. Hence we struggle day to day relentlessly to Research and better our techniques and technology to develop with the best mode of Treatment ensuring fast recovery as well as assuring safety of the patient. Human nails do not have only protective and decorative role, but can Also be considered as an alternative pathway for drug delivery, especially in nail Diseases such as onychomycosis or psoriasis. These nail diseases are widely spread in The population, particularly among elderly and immune-compromised patients. Although the architecture and composition of the nail plate severely limits penetration Of drugs and in addition to that only a fraction of topical drug penetrates across the nail, Oral therapies are accompanied by systemic side effects and drug interactions. For the Successful treatment of nail disease the applied active drug must permeate through the Dense keratinized nail plate and reach deeper layers, the nail bed and the nail matrix [1] Major challenges of drug delivery

to the nail (ungual drug delivery), with the lack of Understanding of both the barrier properties of the nail and formulations to achieve Enhanced unguinal delivery restricting the efficiency of topical treatments for nail Disorders. And also suffer from low patient compliance due to the long treatment Periods (up to 4-8 months) which are required. However, existing oral formulations typically contain large doses of Active ingredients and also require long treatment, creating the potential for systemic Toxicity especially in the liver. Thus, developing more effective methods for nail drug Delivery is an important objective for the pharmaceutical industry.[2]

Structure of human nail

The chemical composition of the human nail severely differs from other body membranes. The plate, composed of keratin molecules with many disulphide linkages and low associated lipid levels, does not resemble any other body membrane in its barrier properties – it tends more like a hydrogel than lipophilic membrane.[3]

fig no 1: structure of human nail

The human nail consists of

- o Nail matrix or the root of the nail
- o Nail bed

- o Eponychium or cuticle
- o Paronychium
- o Hyponychium

o Nail plate.

[4,5]

Functions of nail:

- A healthy nail protects the distal phalanx, the finger tip, and the surrounding tissues from the injuries.
- It helps to enhance delicate movements of the distal digits through counter pressure exerted on the pulp of the finger.
- The nail acts as a counterforce when the end of the finger touches an object and hence enhancing the sensitivity of the fingertip.
- Without nails on the fingertips, it is not possible to grab and hold the things accurately or precisely. (6-7)

Onychomycosis

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail unit. When dermatophytes cause onychomycosis, this condition is called tinea unguium. The term onychomycosis encompasses the dermatophytes, yeasts, and saprophytic mold infections. An abnormal nail not caused by a fungal infection is a dystrophic nail. Onychomycosis can infect both fingernails and toenails, but onychomycosis of the toenail is much more prevalent.

Fig no 2: Structure of onychomycosis

1.5 Classification of Onychomycosis

Fig no 3: type of onychomycosis

A. Distal subungual onychomycosis

The most common form of Tinea unguium is distal subungual. Distal subungual onychomycosis may develop in the toenails, fingernails or both. The infection is usually caused by *Trichophyton rubrum*, which invades the nail bed and the underside of the nailplate, beginning at the

hyponychium and then migrating proximally through the underlying nail matrix. Susceptibility to distal superficial onychomycosis may occur in an autosomal dominant pattern within families.

B. White superficial onychomycosis

White superficial onychomycosis C. Proximal subungual onychomycosis Proximal subungual onychomycosis occurs when the infecting organism, usually *T. rubrum*, invades the nail unit through the proximal nail fold, penetrates the newly formed nail plate and then migrates distally. Fingernails and toenails are equally affected. This form of onychomycosis usually occurs in immune compromised persons and is considered a clinical marker of human immunodeficiency virus infection.

C. **Candida onychomycosis**

Candida onychomycosis can be divided into three general categories. Infection beginning as a paronychia (also called a “whitlow”), the most common type of *Candida* onychomycosis.

D. **Total dystrophic onychomycosis**

Total dystrophic onychomycosis may be the end result of any of the four main forms of onychomycosis.[8,9]

Diagnosis of Onychomycosis

Conventional methods for identifying fungal organisms in the nail plate of patients with onychomycosis (OM) include direct microscopy (after potassium hydroxide solution incubation), fungal culture, and histopathology (using Periodic Acid Schiff [PAS] stain). Surgical pathology testing (of the subungual nail bed and/or the nail plate) using PAS stain is the current gold standard (approaching 100% sensitivity) for the diagnosis of OM. Newer methods for diagnosing OM include polymerase chain reaction (which has a very high specificity), optical coherence tomography, confocal laser scan microscopy, matrix- assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS), and phase contrast hard x-ray microscopy. Confirmation of observations and availability and

cost must be considered before these newer methods for diagnosing OM can be incorporated in clinical practice. [10,11,12]

Treatments of Onychomycosis

Onychomycosis is a term that encompasses all the nail pathologies caused by fungi and accounts for approximately 50% of all nail diseases [13]. The treatment of onychomycosis is a challenging task to patients and professionals as the infection is embedded within the nail. It may take a year or more to get cure as new nail growth must completely replace the old and infected one. Also because of the difficulty in attaining a definitive cure and the high recurrence rate. Patients greater than 55 years of age may have a higher rate of relapse.

- Oral therapy
- Topical therapy [14,15,16]

Nail Lacquer

Topical nail preparations like lacquers, varnishes, enamels etc. are generally used to enhance beauty of nails, imparting color and luster to nail. But in recent times medicated lacquers are specially designed for the nail. These preparations are generally used in fungal diseases. Use of this system avoids oral toxicity of anti-fungal drugs.[17] Medicated nail lacquers are the formulations that have maximal antifungal efficacy as a transungual drug delivery system. After application, the solvent from the lacquer formulation evaporates leaving an occlusive film on which the drug concentration is higher than in the original formulation. This increases the diffusion gradient and permeation through dense keratinized nail plate.[18]

- **Advantages**

1. It cannot be easily removed by rubbing or washing.
2. In addition, the effect is long lasting; single application of lacquer provides protection for one week.
3. Preparation is easy as compared to oral dosage form.
4. Minimal or no systemic side effects.

• **Disadvantages**

- 1 Rashes relate to adverse effects such as periungual erythema and erythema of the proximal nail fold were reported most frequently.
- 2 Other adverse effects which were thought to be casually related include nail disorder such as shape change, irritation, ingrown toe nail and discoloration.[19]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Tea tree oil, ethyl cellulose, Ethyl acetate, salicylic acid, potassium hydrogen phthalate and Castor oil.

METHOD:

Preparation of nail lacquer

The formulation trial is were done as per formula given in table no 4. The medicated nail lacquer was prepared by simple mixing method . The film forming polymer ethyl cellulose was dissolved in ethyl acetate using stirring. The polymer was allowed to dissolved completely, then plasticizer (dibutyl phthalate) was added to the solution while stirring [20]. Castor oil and tea tree oil were added into the polymer solution. Further, salicylic acid and glycerin were added in the desired amount and mixed properly using magnetic stirrer. The formulation was then filled in the narrow mouth containers and sealed with liner and cap. The developed nail lacquer was further optimized to arrive at the final formulation containing desired levels of film former and release retardant

Table no: 1 formulation of nail lacquer

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
Ethyl cellulose	0.5 g	0.7 g	1.0 g
Ethyl acetate	7.0 ml	6.5 ml	6.0 ml
Tea tree oil	0.3 ml	0.5 ml	0.7 ml
Castor oil	1.0 ml	1.0 ml	1.0 ml
Potassium hydrogen phthalate	0.1 g	0.1 g	0.1 g
Salicylic acid	0.1 g	0.3 g	0.5 g

fig no : 4 formulation of nail lacquer

Evaluation test

a. Physical appearance

Visual observations were made of the formulations' color, transparency, and application characteristics.

b. Drying time:

The drying time is the primary test used for the nail lacquer. Briefly a brush applicator was used to

spread the lacquer on a 2 cm Area on a glass slide at room temperature and let to dry. After every 15 sec, a gloved finger was used to touch the film. The time required To obtain dry to touch condition was recorded [21].

c. Smoothness to flow:

The sample was spread on the glass slide. The glass slide was Then raised vertically [22].

d. Gloss:

The sample covered the nail in an even layer. The gloss and the Marketed cosmetic nail lacquer were visually compared.

e. Non- volatile content:

A glass petri plate was used for the sample measurement, and the weight was recorded. The plate was then heated for one hour at 105C. After an hour, the plate's weight was recorded. The difference Between initial and final weight was calculated. The percentage non-Volatile content was determined by formula:

$$\% \text{ non -volatile content} = \frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100$$

f. Water resistance test:

A glass plate was used to apply the sample. After being weighed, The glass plate containing the fully dried sample was submerged in Water. The sample was examined visually for discoloration, turbidity, Blistering, and weight change.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the present study was to formulate a nail lacquer for preventing fungal growth on toe nails or finger nails so that the appearance of the nails is improved. Hence utilizing Tea tree oil and castor oil as anti- inflammatory and anti-fungal a medicated nail lacquer is formulated to provide the

requisite sustained medication release, better drug permeation, and desirable anti-fungal effectiveness. The prepared formulation included salicylic acid as keratolytic agent and permeation enhancer, potassium hydrogen phthalate as plasticizer, release modifying polymers (Ethyl cellulose), and ethyl acetate as a solvent system. Initially, a solvent system was selected for optimization of formulation.

a) Evaluation of Nail lacquer:

Formulated nail lacquers were subjected to preliminary evaluation tests.

b) Physical appearance

Visual observations were made of the formulations' color, transparency, and application characteristics.(fig 5)

figure no: 5 physical appearance

c) Drying Time

Drying time for formulations F1 to F3 was found between 30 seconds to 50 seconds. It was found that as the polymer concentration increases from 0.5 % w/v to 1 % w/v the drying time increases respectively. The time required for the solvent to evaporate from the more viscous solution is more than the less viscous solution. Formulation F2 showed optimum drying time of about 40 sec. Formulation F3 showed maximum drying time as it contained higher amount of polymer.

Table no 2: Drying time of various batches

Batch	Ethyl cellulose (gm)	Drying time (sec)
F1	0.5 g	30 sec
F2	0.7 g	40 sec
F3	1.0 g	50 sec

d) Smoothness to flow and gloss

Optimized formulation F2 when poured onto the glass plate was found to have satisfactory flow property and result in a uniform smooth film, as compared to other formulation batches.

Figure no: 6 gloss of appearance

e) Non- Volatile Content of Nail Lacquer

The increase in polymer concentration from 0.5 % to 1 % causes increase in non-volatile content of nail lacquer. Non- Volatile Content depends on polymer content. Thus, higher the polymer concentration higher is the non-volatile content of nail Lacquer.

f) Water Resistance Test

As shown in, Table 5 increase in polymer concentration increase the water resistance. Formulation F1, F1and F2 shows lower water resistance than F3.

Table no: 3 water resistant test

Formulation batch	W ^a 1 (gm)	W ^{2b} (gm)	Difference in weight (gm)
F1	5.25	5.35	0.10
F2	5.25	5.40	0.15
F3	5.25	5.44	0.19

CONCLUSION

The formulated herbal nail lacquer demonstrated satisfactory physical properties, including acceptable drying time and film stability. The presence of tea tree oil contributed to antifungal efficacy, showing potential against common nail pathogens like *Candida albicans* or *Trichophyton* species. Incorporation of castor oil enhanced the cosmetic appeal and conditioning effect on nails. The formulation was stable, easy to apply, and offered therapeutic potential for the treatment and prevention of onychomycosis and other minor nail infections. Thus, the herbal nail lacquer represents

a promising alternative to conventional chemical-based treatments, combining therapeutic efficacy with cosmetic benefits. From the above studies, it can be concluded that medicated nail lacquers proved to be a better tool as a drug delivery system for the unguinal drug delivery of an antifungal in the treatment of onychomycosis. Apart from treating the nail infections, the medicated nail lacquers can be also used for beautification of nails with ease of application. This improves patient compliance and acceptability.

REFERENCES

1. Gupchup GV, Zatz JL. Structural characteristics and permeability properties of the human nail: a review. *J Cosmet Sci.* 1999;50:363–85.
2. Patel RP, Naik SA, Patel NA, Suthar AM. Drug delivery across human nail. *Int J Curr Pharm Res.* 2009;1(1):1–7.
3. Ashwini R. Department of Pharmaceutics, Karnataka College of Pharmacy, Bangalore-560064, India. 200.
4. Gaikwad PS, Pagare RV. Pravara Rural Education Society's College of Pharmacy, Chincholi, Nashik. 464.
5. Rathi AR, Popat RR, Adhao VS, Shrikhande VN. Nail lacquer delivery system: a review. *Int J Pharm Edu Res.* 2020;54(1):9. doi:10.18231/j.ijpen.2020.0029.
6. Nail anatomy [Internet]. Wikipedia; c2021 [cited 2021 Apr]. Available from: <http://en.wikipedia.org>.
7. Kumar V, Sharma S, Naveen, Jalwal P. A comprehensive review on human nail. *Int J Med Health.* 2017;3(10):72–4.
8. Shirwaikar AA, Thomas TA, Lobo R, Prabhu KS. Treatment of onychomycosis: an update. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2008;70(6):710–4.
9. Kobayashi Y, Komastu T, Sumi M, Numajiri S, Miyamoto M, Kobayashi D, et al. In vitro permeation of several drugs through the human nail plate: relationship between physicochemical properties and nail permeability. *Eur J Pharm Sci.* 2004;21:471–7.
10. Westerberg DP, Voyack MJ. Onychomycosis: current trends in diagnosis and treatment. *Am Fam Physician.* 2013;88(11):762–70.
11. Weinberg JM, Koestenblatt EK, Tutrone WD, Tishler HR, Najarian L. Comparison of diagnostic methods in the evaluation of onychomycosis. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2003;49(2):193–7.
12. Elewski BE, Hay RJ. Update on the management of onychomycosis: highlights of the Third Annual International Summit on Cutaneous Antifungal Therapy. *Clin Infect Dis.* 1996;23(2):305–13.
13. Gregoriou S, Kyriazopoulou M, Tsiogka A, Rigopoulos D. Novel and investigational treatments for onychomycosis. *J Fungi.* 2022;8(10):1079. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8101079>.
14. Piraccini BM, Alessandrini A. Onychomycosis: a review. *J Fungi.* 2015;1(1):30–43.
15. Monti D, Tampucci S, Paganini V, Burgalassi S, Chetoni P, Galván J, et al. Ciclopirox hydroxypropyl chitosan (CPX - HPCH) nail lacquer and breathable cosmetic nail polish: in vitro evaluation of drug transungual permeation following the combined application. *Life.* 2022;12(6):849.
16. Puri V, Savla R, Chen K, Robinson K, Virani A, Michniak-Kohn B. Antifungal nail lacquer for enhanced transungual delivery of econazole nitrate. *Pharmaceutics.* 2022;14(10):2204.
17. Verma NK, Roshan A. Department of Pharmacy, Rameshwaram Institute of Technology and Management, Lucknow (U.P.), India; Faculty of Pharmacy, Varanasi College of Pharmacy, Varanasi (U.P.), India.
18. Rathi AR, Popat RR, Adhao VS, Shrikhande VN. Nail drug delivery system: a review. *Int J Pharm Chem Anal.* 2020;7(1):11–2. doi:10.18231/j.ijpca.2020.002.
19. Mali VM, Alhat SJ. Formulation and evaluation of beetroot-based nail polish. *Int J Sci Res Eng Med.* 2021;7(5):3930–6.
20. American Pharmaceutical Association. Handbook of pharmaceutical excipients.

Washington, DC: American Pharmaceutical Association; 1986. p. 210, 262, 592.

21. Puri V, Savla R, Chen K, Robinson K, Virani A, Michniak-Kohn B. Antifungal nail lacquer for enhanced transungual delivery of econazole nitrate. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022;14(10):2204.
22. Farsana P, Shahanas B, Sebastian A, George AM. Formulation and evaluation of medicated tolnaftate nail lacquer. *Glob J Med Res B*. 2018;18(5):1–6.

HOW TO CITE: Vaishnavi Wazulkar*, Ankita Jadhav, Swati Deshmukh, Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Nail Lacquer for Treatment of Onychomycosis, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 2171-2179. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15398260>

